

Spectrophotometric Studies on Mono- and Di-Nuclear Complexes of Rhenium with α -Thiopicolinamide-(2-Pyridyl)

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The ligand, α -thiopicolinamide-(2-pyridyl), (Thiopic), forms both mononuclear (1:3) and di-nuclear (2:1) complexes with rhenium in +5 oxidation state. The overall stability constants, β_{13} of 1:3 and β_{21} of 2:1 complexes are 7.60×10^{12} and 1.07×10^8 respectively. Thiopic forms a brownish yellow complex in 0.15–1.5 N HCl in presence of SnCl_2 in 50 percent aqueous acetonitrile solvent system. The 1:3 complex can be utilised for determination of rhenium in the range 1-12 ppm, with sensitivity (Sandell's) $0.027 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$.

FEW reagents like unithiol¹, dithiol², α -fural dioxime³, thioglycollic acid⁴, thiosalicylic acid⁵ and 8-mercaptoquinoline⁶ are considered promising for spectrophotometric determination of rhenium. Of these, only 8-mercaptoquinoline has been proved to be very useful for estimation of rhenium. Except for thiosalicylic acid, no data regarding the metal ligand ratio of the complexes formed are available. No works except ours, has been done upto date to ascertain the stepwise stability constants of rhenium complexes, nor any work has so far been attempted to determine stability constants by spectrophotometric method for 2:1 or 1:3 metal-ligand systems. Moreover, rhenium in trace amounts are found in biological system. So it is all the more necessary to determine rhenium when present in small amounts and to determine the stability constants as well. By proper extension of Leden's method, the overall as well as stepwise stability constants for 2:1 and 1:3 complexes have been evaluated.

Experimental

Apparatus: All the spectral measurements were carried out with the Hilger-Uvispek spectrophotometer using matched 1 cm glass cells.

Reagents: Standard solution of rhenium was prepared by dissolving KReO_4 (Johnson & Mathey, 99.9% pure) in twice distilled water. The solution contained 1.00 mg of Re per ml. Working solutions were prepared as needed by dilution of the stock solution. The reagent, thiopic, was prepared following Porter's method⁷. A freshly prepared 0.025% (w/v) acetonitrile solution of the yellow reagent was used for the studies. A 5.8% SnCl_2 solution was prepared by dissolving 7 g of $\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (A.R.) in 8.5 ml of conc. (12N HCl) and diluted to 100 ml.

Recommended procedures: To a 25.0 ml volumetric flask containing 0.05 mg to 0.3 mg of rhenium as

ReO_4^- , add 0.54 ml of concentrated HCl and 6.5 ml of acetonitrile. Cool at room temperature, add 6 ml of 0.025% (w/v) of thiopic solution in acetonitrile and shake. Run 6 ml of 5.8% (w/v) of SnCl_2 in the flask and dilute to 25 ml with water. Allow the colour to develop for 30 min and measure the absorbance at 380 nm against reagent blank.

The visible absorption spectra of the complex prepared by the recommended procedure stated earlier in 50% aqueous-acetonitrile solvent system are recorded. The spectra are representative of that found for all ReO_4^- concentrations cited in this work in presence of excess of SnCl_2 , HCl, and ligand used. The medium is restricted to 50% aqueous-acetonitrile, as it is optimum amount; if the amount of water is increased, turbidity appears. The reagent solution has very low absorbance. Thus the reagent blank is also taken into consideration. The absorbance of the complex gradually decreases as the wavelength increases. The optimum wavelength is 380 nm, where other spectral studies are performed.

Study of variables: It has been found that the order of addition is not important except that the SnCl_2 must be added last. Low results were obtained if the reagent is added last because of the formation of some Re(IV) . For maximum colour development a minimum of 4 ml of 5.8% (w/v) SnCl_2 solution in 1N HCl is required for the maximum colour development. There is no appreciable change in the absorbance upto 10 ml of SnCl_2 solution.

For maximum colour development 0.15N–1.5N acid medium is suitable. At higher concentrations of acid above 1.5N HCl the absorbance decreases, while at lower concentrations of acid below 0.14N HCl turbidity occurs.

The effect of reagent concentration on the absorbance of the rhenium complex at 0.5N HCl was studied. The absorbance gradually increases upto 4 ml of the

reagent, after that there is no change in the absorbance even upto 10 ml. For all subsequent measurements, 6 ml of 0.025% (w/v) reagent were always used. The colour reaction has been found to be dependent on time, acid concentration and temperature. For full colour development, it takes 20 min and becomes constant after 20 min. The complex is stable for at least 20 hr in the said solvent system.

Beer's law, optical range and sensitivity: Test solutions with different concentrations of rhenium (1-15 ppm) were prepared by recommended procedure. The system obeyed Beer's law from 1 to 12 ppm.

The optimal concentration range for measurement was found by Ringbom's method to be 3-12 ppm of rhenium. The molar absorptivity was found to be 6797. The sensitivity of the colour reaction was 0.027 μg of Re/cm², according to Sandell's definition.

Accuracy of the method: Accuracy of the method was studied by analysing solutions containing known amounts of rhenium by recommended procedure. The results of this investigation are summarised as follows.

Rhenium taken ppm	Rhenium found ppm	Relative Error %
4.00	3.97	-0.75%
8.00	8.02	+0.50%

Each result is the average of three separate analysis.

Effect of diverse ions: The effect of diverse ions on the rhenium determination was studied by adding 400 ppm of the ion in question to a solution containing 8 ppm of rhenium as ReO₄⁻ and proceeding as in the general procedure. It has been observed that 200 ppm of coloured ions like Cu²⁺, Co²⁺, Ni²⁺, Fe³⁺, Fe₂, 400 ppm of Mn²⁺, Zn²⁺, Cr³⁺, V⁵⁺, 200 ppm of W⁶⁺ and 60 ppm of Mo⁶⁺, Br³⁺, Ti⁴⁺, etc., do not interfere. Among the anions only thiocyanate and nitrate interfere seriously, the interference due to thiocyanate can be overcome by treating the sample with alkaline peroxide followed by heating to remove excess peroxide.

Composition of the complex: Determination of ligand-to-metal ratio in mixed solvent system was found to be reproducible at different ReO₄⁻ concentrations.

Job's method of continuous variation clearly indicates the existence of two types of complexes, i.e., mononuclear (1 : 3) and dinuclear (2 : 1) complexes. Fig. 1 shows one of these curves at 380 nm in which equimolar solutions of (Re = 4 = 8.55 × 10⁻⁴ M) were utilized. The composition was further verified by molar ratio method. Since there is existence of dinuclear species, reverse molar ratio method was also performed. From the Job's, molar ratio and reverse molar ratio method data, it is evident that the mononuclear (1 : 3) complex is the predominant one at excess concentration of ligand

whereas dinuclear (2 : 1), one is at excess concentration of metal.

Fig. 1. Job's Plot M = R = 8.055 × 10⁻⁴ M.

Stepwise formation constants of Rhenium-Thiocyanate complexes: The stepwise formation constants have been calculated for 1 : 3 system by extension of Ledon's method⁸ using spectrophotometric data. The free metal and free ligand concentrations were calculated by considering the following equilibrium reaction :

The degree of complex formation function for 1 : 3 and 2 : 1 system is given by the following equation :

$$\frac{C_M}{M} = \phi + 1 + \beta_{11}L + \beta_{12}L^2 + \beta_{13}L^3 + 2\beta_{21}ML \quad \dots (2)$$

Therefore,

$$\psi_1 = \beta_{11} + \beta_{12}L + \beta_{13}L^2 + 2\beta_{21}M \quad \dots (3)$$

The value of $K_{11} = \beta_{11}$ was obtained by plotting $\psi_1(L)_M$ as ordinate against free ligand L and extrapolating to zero ligand concentration, and found to be $\beta_{11} = K_{11} = 1.20 \times 10^4$. Similarly the values of β_{12} and β_{13} were obtained by plotting the functions $\psi_2(L)_M$ and $\psi_3(L)_M$ respectively, while ψ_2 and ψ_3 are calculated as :

$$\psi_2(L)_M = \frac{\psi_1 - \beta_{11}}{L}$$

and

$$\psi_3(L)_M = \frac{\psi_2 - \beta_{12}}{L}$$

The values of β_{12} and β_{13} were found to be 1.70×10^8 and 7.60×10^{12} respectively, (Fig. 2.).

Thus

$$k_{12} = 1.54 \times 10^4 \text{ and } k_{13} = 4.46 \times 10^4.$$

The stepwise formation constants for dinuclear species was obtained from a set of experiments in which reagent concentration was fixed and the metal

Fig. 2. Plots of ψ_1 and ψ_2 obtained from Leden's method. Plot for ψ_3 obtained from Leden's method.

concentration always in excess, was varied. From equation (3) ψ_1 was calculated, and the stability constant for dinuclear species were obtained from the plots of functions $\psi_1(M)_L$ against free metal concentration for number of values of L , which gave a straight line of intercept β_{11} when $M \rightarrow 0$ and a slope of $2\beta_{21}$ (Fig. 3).

$$\therefore \psi_1^0 = \lim_{M \rightarrow 0} \psi_1(M)_L = \beta_{11} = 1.50 \times 10^4 = k_{11}$$

$$\text{Slope} = 2\beta_{21} = 2.15 \times 10^8$$

$$\therefore \beta_{21} = 1.07 \times 10^8$$

and

$$k_{21} = 7.13 \times 10^8.$$

Fig. 3. Subsidiary function $\psi_1(M)_L$ as a function of free metal concentration, M .

The values obtained for k_{11} , k_{12} and k_{13} are of the same order which suggest that all the three ligands co-ordinate with rhenium(V) simultaneously to give 1:3 complex. The complex mainly dominates in the solution as $[\text{Re } L_3]\text{Cl}_2$ or $[\text{Re } L_3]\text{SO}_4$ according to the acid medium.

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